

IWA World Water Congress & Exhibition 2024

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Exploring the valorisation potential of urban wastewater in Flanders by the application of a 2-stage technology

L. Dockx*, S., Moreno Sayavedra**, I., Sigurnjak**, B., Saerens*, E., Meers**, and B., De Bock*

* Aquafin NV

** RE-SOURCE LAB, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, Ghent University

inspiring change

WALNUT'S AMBITION

WalNUT aims to **redesign** the value and supply chain of nutrients from **wastewater** and **brine**, creating solutions for **nutrient recovery** while contributing to a **circular economy** and sustainability in the **EU agricultural sector**.

Start: September 2021

End: February 2026

Duration: 54 months

WASTEWATER IS NOT WASTED

The project will test **new technologies** with four different wastewater streams: **urban and sewage sludge**, **food**, **industrial** and **brine** in order to **close water cycles for nutrient recovery**.

WALNUT'S CONSORTIUM

BIO**P**HOSPHATE
100% NATURAL

Aquafin

CARTIF

CETAQUA
WATER TECHNOLOGY CENTRE

AGRICULTURES
& TERRITOIRES
CHAMPIERS D'AGRICULTURE

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UNIVERSITY OF COPENHAGEN

GHENT
UNIVERSITY

AGRINNOVA
RESEARCH BEARS ITS FRUITS

VEOLIA

AQUAFIN

Wastewater transport,
treatment and reuse

Rainwater management

Climate adaptation and
mitigation

WATER QUALITY IN FLANDERS

*“Expanding, maintaining and replacing the **Flemish wastewater treatment infrastructure** is a job we do not manage on our own. Each year Aquafin brings hundreds of projects to the market for technical partners and suppliers. This joint effort pays off. **The quality of the water bodies in Flanders has improved tremendously over the past decades.**”*

THE POTENTIAL OF URBAN WASTEWATER

"Aquafin works towards streams and brooks full of life and a living environment in harmony with water."

WHY SHOULD WE RECOVER RESOURCES?

Resources in Flemish urban wastewater per year (5.5 mio PE)

230 ktonne COD

**GHG emission
Energy consumption**

28 ktonne N

**1-2% of global energy
use**

3.9 ktonne P

**World reserves under
pressure, geopolitics**

10 ktonne K

**World reserves for ± 100
years**

ELIMINATING STEPS IN THE N-CYCLE

- Nitrogen fixation by Haber-Bosch → 1-2% of global energy consumption
- Wastewater treatment by nitrification/denitrification → 1% emitted as N_2O

0.7% electricity use of Flanders

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CONCEPT: A 2-STAGE TECHNOLOGY

- Why HRAS?
 - Lower oxygen supply/dosage (and energy consumption) + increase in energy potential of sludge ↔ CAS
 - C-uptake by sludge, almost no nutrient removal (N and P)
- Why IEX?
 - Frequently used in the context of nutrient recovery
 - Applicable to streams with various N-concentrations
 - Specific adsorption possible

A CRITICAL ASSESSMENT

- Is the combination of HRAS + IEX feasible?
- Type of wastewater streams:
 - Effluent
 - HRAS + IEX → recovery
 - CAS + IEX → “polishing”
 - Centrate from anaerobic digestion
- HRAS + IEX ↔ CAS + N-stripping/scrubbing

IN PRACTICE

- HRAS (stage 1) + IEX (stage 2) at WWTP of Aartselaar (54,000 PE)
 - Fully-automated
 - Biological treatment of 1m³ of raw wastewater per day - SBR
 - IEX configuration allows a bed volume of 1.8-7L
 - Natural zeolites (aluminosilicate mineral, Na⁺ and H⁺ form)
 - Granular size: 0.2-1mm
 - IEX configuration includes the regeneration (3 w/v% KCl) of the zeolites

RESULTS

HRAS (stage 1)

Biomethane potential: 125 → 213 Nm³ CH₄/ton dw

- Conversion of CAS into HRAS at pilot scale
 - Organic loading rate: 0.2 → 2.5 gbCOD/gVSS.d
 - Sludge retention time: 22 → 2 d
- Results
 - A stable BOD-removal over time
 - A decrease in N-removal as a result of reduced nitrification
 - Suspended solids (> 35 mg/L) in effluent, limited P-removal

< 0.1% kg N₂O/
kg KjN_{removed}

Low energy input
(0.4 kWh/m³)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000752

RESULTS

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Bioresource Technology

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■ IEX (stage 2)

Post-treatment of high-rate activated sludge effluent via zeolite adsorption and recovery of ammonium-nitrogen as alternative fertilising products

Sarah Moreno Sayavedra^{a,*}, Lennert Dockx^b, Ivona Sigurnjak^a, Çağrı Akyol^a, Erik Meers^a

^a Department of Green Chemistry and Technology, Ghent University, Coupure links 653, 9000 Ghent, Belgium

^b Aquafin NV, Dijkstraat 8, 2630 Aartselaar, Belgium

HIGHLIGHTS

- A novel NH_4^+ recovery system combining HRAS/CS and adsorption was tested.
- 70–80 % of NH_4^+ in HRAS/CS effluent was recovered in outputs after treating 140 BV.
- Zeolite and regeneration effluent also contained between 0.2–1.8 % K.
- Regeneration effluent from NH_4^+ desorption could be applied in fertigation.
- N-saturated zeolite has potential as various fertilising products according to FPR.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
Ammonium recovery
Ion-exchange
High-rate contact-stabilization
Municipal wastewater
Circular economy

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the potential to connect nutrient flows between wastewater treatment and agriculture through a two-stage nitrogen (N) recovery system composed of high-rate activated sludge treatment in contact stabilisation mode (HRAS/CS) and column adsorption with zeolite. The HRAS/CS process removes organic matter and suspended solids in wastewater, leaving N behind in the effluent. The N was successfully recovered with the zeolite column under different scenarios, generating N and K-rich by-products. The regeneration effluent from the zeolite column with KCl contained 60–845 mg NH_4^+ -N/L and 1.6–14.3 g K/L, having potential for use as fertigation water. The N-saturated zeolite contained 1.5–8.4 mg N/g and 14.3–19.3 mg K/g of the product fresh weight and low contaminant content, making it potentially eligible as various fertilising products. Adsorption can thus concentrate N from HRAS/CS effluent and produce by-products with potential agricultural value while meeting chemical oxygen demand and total nitrogen discharge standards.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000752

RESULTS

- IEX (stage 2)
 - Lab-scale: adsorption material

RESULTS

IEX (stage 2)

— Lab-scale: breakthrough curves/isotherms

Breakthrough V = 80% $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ removal

Similar q_{\max} (best 5-25 BV/h)

Moreno Sayavedra, S., et al. (2024) *Post-treatment of high-rate activated sludge effluent via zeolite adsorption and recovery of ammonium-nitrogen as alternative fertilising products*. Bioresource Technology

RESULTS

- IEX (stage 2)
 - Concentrations of recovered N are rather low
 - DoE

BBFs produced with the 2-stage system

1.4-8.4 mg N/g FW zeolites (solid)
25-845 mg N/L (liquid)

RESULTS

- N-stripping pilot at WWTP of Antwerp-South (171,000 PE)
 - 1 m³ of centrate per batch (+/- 1400 mg N/L)
 - Average recovery efficiency of
 - 56%, without caustic dosage, pH = 8.4
 - 85%, with caustic dosage, pH = 9.2

Example: 55°C without caustic dosage

Cost calculation	Average (€/kg N)
Direct costs	12.1
Direct gains	0.3
Indirect costs	1.1
Indirect gains	0.6
Total cost balance	12.2

TAKE HOME MESSAGES

- N-recovery is a matter of **optimizing costs and environmental impact**
 - Feasible
 - Desirable
 - CO₂-footprint
 - Avoiding emissions (e.g. N₂O)
 - Profitable
- Limited (and restrictive) **legislation**

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Thank you for your attention!

Contact: lennert.dockx@aquafin.be

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Two-stage system

